

THE CONTRIBUTION OF THEORY AND RESEARCH TO THE TRANSFORMATION OF LIBRARIES

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LIBRARY COMMUNICATION IN THE SOCIO-CULTURAL SPACE OF MODERN SOCIETY

Objective. To represent library communication in the socio-cultural space of modern society. **Methods.** The methodology of the article was based on a set of general and special methods of scientific knowledge. **Results.** We substantiated the essence and content of the term "library communication" as a pre-planned activity in the socio-cultural space of modern society. There are presented the structural content elements of library communication: goal, objective, essence, driving mechanism, purpose, implementation, basic tools, main communication product, indifferent components, sources, environment and specifics of functioning, levels and result. We established that library practice today is constantly enriched with new phenomena and concepts to denote them, for which library science as a science should formulate appropriate terms, provide theoretical and methodological justification. **Conclusions.** It is argued that in the context of the theory of social communications, the institutionalization of the term "library communication" as a separate type of professional communication and the driving force of the transformation of the library business is relevant.

Keywords: library; library communication; information society

Introduction

The information and communication activity of the library as a unique social institution, whose mission is realized through the transfer of culturally significant and science-intensive information, in the conditions of accelerated scientific-technical and technological progress undergoes significant transformations. These changes are expressed in the mutual optimization of the internal structure and external relations of the library, which is embodied in new products and services for the successful development and maintenance of competitive advantages in the market based on optimal algorithms. Transformation of the postulates of the past and interpretation of modern theories of communication in the context of the information and library sphere is an important task of today's library science as a science of library genesis and evolution. "According to the new paradigm in library science, the modern library is part of the system of social communications of society, which is formed by institutions that are associated with any means of recording and processing documents, information and knowledge and contribute to social consciousness and social intelligence" (authors' transl.) (Davydova, 2013).

It is worth emphasizing the presence of significant scientific achievements in relation to the communication essence of the library, its communicative practices and functions. In the scientific discourse we have not found a separate study of the essential characteristics of library communication (hereinafter LC), its structural elements. In general, the work of librarians is concentrated around the content and directions of communication (information and communication) activities of libraries. "Terminological issues regarding the qualification of library science, as a rule, remain out of the attention of scholars" (authors' transl.) (Shvetsova-Vodka, 2019b).

Methods

The methodology of the article was based on a set of general and special methods of scientific knowledge. The structural-functional method is used to identify the content elements of library communication. The dialectical method presents the progress of the library as a socio-communicative system of the information society. The use of the methodology of terminological analysis (Pshenichna & Shishkina, 2004) whose object is not the object itself, but deliberately processed information about it, including properties, features of the object and the subject field of its operation, allowed to propose a definition of the term “library communication”. In general, the term “library communication” in the discipline-specific terminology that serves scientific theory has reasonable prospects. The application of methods of analysis and synthesis made it possible to identify the main current trends in the development of library communication.

Analysis of recent research. A significant contribution to the study of the coevolution of science and scientific communication of libraries was made by G. Shemayeva (2008, 2009, 2015). Exploring the theoretical and methodological foundations of the communicative function of the library for the organization of its system-integration interaction with open science, V. Kopaneva (2017) presented the expansion of the communicative activity of the scientific library for it to ensure, along with preservation and free distribution, full cycle of new knowledge, at all stages of the research process. T. Granchak (2012) analyzed the participation of libraries and their information-analytical structures in the processes of political communication, outlining the priority areas for the development of libraries in the system of political communication. The main trends in the development of library communication models (hereinafter LCM) of domestic higher education institutions in terms of informatization and their integration into a single communication space of the information society are identified by T. Kolesnikova (2013). LCM of higher education institutions are considered as a set of purposeful processes of exchange of basic means of communication (documents, information, knowledge) in appropriate forms, transmitted through communication channels, reproduced in the relevant traffic flow patterns and determined by certain communication links within the existing communication environments. Important in the context of the chosen topic is the scientific work of I. O. Davydova (2014) on the study of library as a communication system and the specifics of its communication processes. We agree with the author that communication is not just an integral part of various areas of library activities, but “its structural affiliation is determined as the most important component of the subsystem, ensuring its integrity and development” (authors' transl.) (Davydova, 2014). The conceptual meaning and etymological nature of the interdisciplinary term “communication” are covered by G. Onufrienko and A. Chernevych (2010). G. Shvetsova-Vodka (2019a, 2019b) generalized modern ideas about sciences that study communication (communication science, communicative studies, noocommunicology), and described the differences between the terminological elements derived from «communication», in particular «book communication» (“a type of social information communication in which the means of transmitting information in society is a book” (authors' transl.)). Thus, from the standpoint of the latest, updated theoretical and methodological research, we define library communication in the socio-cultural space of modern society.

Results and Discussion

In the context of global digitalization, fundamental for the progress of the library as a socio-communicative system of the information society and a full-fledged subject of the national

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humanitarian space is the development of library communication, which has not yet acquired a systemically controlled character in the domestic library-information sphere, despite the diversification (the Neo-Latin diversificatio - change, diversity; from diversus - different and facere - to do) of library production.

The ambiguity of the word “communication” (Latin *communicatio* – unity, transmission, connection) is embodied in such concepts as 1) the way of communication (air); 2) form of communication (telephone); 3) the act of communication, information notification. That is, we treat communication as an information exchange. “The processes of globalization and informatization, in which the amount of human knowledge is at least doubled every year, stimulate multi-parameter and fundamental linguistic research of such a multidimensional phenomenon as communication – a process of active and accelerated information exchange. The term «communication» is the basis for the creation of a number of derivative heterogeneous term units according to different models” (authors' transl.) (Onufrienko & Chernevych, 2010), one of which is “library communication”. Given the fair maxim of G. Onufrienko and A. Chernevych (2010) that “the conceptual essence [of the term “communication”] is determined by professional discourse”, we consider it appropriate in the library-information sphere to use the term “library communication” in the context of innovative ideas of digitalization and requirements of the knowledge society. The proposed word-forming model corresponds to the laws of the Ukrainian language, and the language practice testifies to the birth of a somewhat different lexical meaning in it.

The successful development of the library, the constitutive feature of which is the adaptive (Latin *adapto* – adjust) nature and its socio-communicative purpose, is advanced by the progress of library communication, as a conceptual basis of its activities, where interactive information exchange processes are decisive. “The communicative nature of libraries is enhanced in the information society, in the future – the knowledge society” (authors' transl.) (Davydova, 2014).

Library communication is a set of pre-planned actions of information and communication activities of the library, the structural content elements of which are as follows:

- ✓ The major *goal* of LC is to strengthen the position of the library in society;
- ✓ The main *objective* of LC is expressed in improving the image of the library in society;
- ✓ The *essence* of LC is to ensure the system and integrity of information and communication activities of the library;
- ✓ The driving *mechanism* of the LC is the establishment of communication links of the library through the development, distribution and use of library products (library-information resources, services, etc.) in the process of information and communication activities;
- ✓ *The purpose* of LC is multifactorial coverage of socio-cultural reality through constant monitoring for the humanization of the consolidated scientific-educational-cultural space;
- ✓ *LC implementation* takes place through direct involvement in the social sphere;
- ✓ The basic *tools* of LC: new models of interaction with potential users, the optimal combination of traditional and modern forms of PR-activities to promote books and reading (book trailer), types of popularization of the library in the community (flash mob) or professional community (scientific conference);
- ✓ *The main communication product* of LC is information focused on information-communication needs of a certain category of users;

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- ✓ The *indifferent components* (English component – part) LC – subject (librarian / library), object (librarian of another library, user, resident (community)), means of communication (including social networks);
- ✓ LC *sources* include a conglomeration of intellectual (key professional competencies of employees involved in library communication), information (services, products), intangible assets (organizational memory, corporate culture, etc.) and material resources (for example, library collection, historical and cultural property where it is located) of a library;
- ✓ LC *environment*: traditional (offline) and up-to-date (online);
- ✓ The *specifics of LC functioning* is a conceptual factor of optimization and modernization of library practice;
- ✓ LC *levels*: internal library and external library;
- ✓ LC *result* is an effective economic development of society and enrichment with new knowledge based on intellectual and spiritual development of a socially adapted citizen with high moral values.

The resourcefulness of library communication, taking into account the integrative nature of the library and the features of new communication channels, is manifested in obtaining the planned desired result, established traditions and proven methods and forms. Library communication, targeted at long-term focus, is a fundamental factor in the functioning of an effective library-information sphere.

“In the context of organizational and structural transformations, when libraries master the electronic space and function in a distributed information environment as network structures, the importance of intra-library and inter-library communications, the responsibility of working groups and multifunctional project teams that carry out innovative activities is increasing” (authors' transl.) (Davydova, 2014).

Conclusions

Today, library practice is constantly enriched with new phenomena and concepts to denote them, for which library science as a science should formulate appropriate terms, provide theoretical and methodological justification. In the context of the theory of social communications, the institutionalization of the concept of “library communication” as a separate type of professional communication and the driving force of the transformation of the library business is relevant. We consider promising the further scientific research to analyze and clarify, taking into account the current circumstances, library communication as a subsystem of a holistic communication system, which is constantly undergoing both internal system changes and external factor influences.

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БІБЛІОТЕЧНА КОМУНІКАЦІЯ В СОЦІОКУЛЬТУРНОМУ ПРОСТОРИ СУЧАСНОГО СУСПІЛЬСТВА

Мета. Репрезентувати бібліотечну комунікацію в соціокультурному просторі сучасного суспільства.
Методика. Методологія статті базувалася на сукупності загальних та спеціальних методів наукового пізнання.
Результати. Обґрунтовано сутність і зміст терміна «бібліотечна комунікація» як заздалегідь спланованої діяльності в соціокультурному просторі сучасного суспільства. Представлено структурні контентні елементи бібліотечної комунікації: мета, ціль, сутність, рушійний механізм, призначення, реалізація, базові інструменти, основний комунікаційний продукт, індиферентні компоненти, джерела, середовище та специфіка функціонування, рівні та результат. Встановлено, що бібліотечна практика сьогодні невпинно збагачується новими явищами та поняттями на їх позначення, яким бібліотекознавство як

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наука повинна сформулювати відповідні терміни, надати теоретико-методологічне обґрунтування.
Висновки. Аргументовано, що у контексті теорії соціальних комунікацій актуальним є інституціалізація терміна «бібліотечна комунікація» як окремого виду професійного спілкування та рушійної сили трансформації бібліотечної справи.

Ключові слова: бібліотека; бібліотечна комунікація; інформаційне суспільство

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